

Anti-ulcerogenic Activity of Aqueous Extract of Unripe Fruit of *Musa sapientum* Linn in Combination with Vitamin C on Ulcer Induced Models in Experimental Rats

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors MEG, OLI and AE designed the study, performed the statistical analysis and wrote the protocol. Author MEG wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors MEG, OLI, AHA and IP managed the analyses of the study and the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aims: To evaluate the effect of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* Linn in combination with Vitamin C on aspirin and ethanol induced ulcer models in Wistar rats.

Study Design: Anti-ulcer study.

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria, between February and April, 2016.

Methodology: Forty-five rats divided into 9 groups of five were used for each model. Doses of 250 mg/kg, 500 mg/kg, and 1000 mg/kg of *Musa sapientum* (MS) alone and in combination with Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (1:1) were administered to the animals, Vitamin C 100 mg/kg was administered to

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another group, while the control group received distilled water. Omeprazole 20 mg/kg was given to a different group. The animals were sacrificed and stomach was removed for examination.

Results: The aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* Linn showed significant ($P<0.05$) decrease in ulcer in both models, which was further enhanced by Vitamin C addition.

Conclusion: This study concludes that Vitamin C potentiates the anti-ulcerogenic effect of unripe fruits of *Musa sapientum* in rats.

Keywords: Ulcer; *Musa sapientum*; aspirin; ethanol; vitamin C.

1. INTRODUCTION

An imbalance between aggressive factors and the maintenance of mucosal integrity via endogenous defence mechanisms is generally accepted as the etiology of peptic ulcer [1,2]. Drugs such the prostaglandin analogues, the proton pump inhibitors, antacids, histamine (H_2) receptor blockers, amongst others are used for ulcer therapy but are shown to have side effects which may limited their use [1].

Many natural products of medicinal herbs are reported to enhance gastric and intestinal mucosal integrity by increasing the mucosal defensive factors. The use of medicinal plants worldwide in the management of diseases is mainly due to their easy access and preparations, low cost, as well as ancestral experience [3].

Musa sapientum (Musaceae), commonly called banana, is a tropical plant whose fruit is widely consumed as a nutritious food across the globe. Earlier anti-ulcerogenic studies of *Musa sapientum* and *Musa* spp have been reported [4-6]. The present study is an evaluation of the effect of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* in combination with Vitamin C on aspirin and ethanol induced ulcer models in Wistar rats.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Animals

Wistar rats of both sexes of an average weight of 220 g were obtained from the colony breed of the animal house of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State. The rats were kept in cages under standard conditions and fed with standard rat feeds (Growers feed) and clean water *ad libitum*. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks, prior to the commencement of the experiments.

2.2 Plants

Fresh unripe fruits of *Musa sapientum* (banana) were bought from the main market in Abraka and were identified and authenticated by Dr. Erhenhi A.H., a taxonomist of the Department of Botany, Faculty of Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka. The unripe banana fruits were cut into pieces, air-dried at room temperature and blended into coarse powder. The powdered *Musa sapientum* (400 g) was dissolved in 1600 ml of distilled water. The solution was stirred every 6 h and allowed to stand for 72 h, after which the solution was filtered using Whatman filter paper and then concentrated to dryness using a rotary evaporator. The percentage yield of *Musa sapientum* was 11.85% w/w.

2.3 Drugs

Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (Em-Vit-C[®]) of the Emzor Pharmaceutical industries Limited and Omeprazole (20 mg/kg) of the Linedge Pharmaceuticals were bought from a pharmacy.

2.4 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Studies

The acute toxicity (LD₅₀) study was carried on the unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* using a modified Lorke's method [7]. Animals of either sex were fasted overnight prior to the study. Dosage selection of up to 5000 mg/kg was used.

2.5 Anti-Ulcerogenic Studies

2.5.1 Aspirin induced ulcer model

A modified method of Sivaraman and Muralidharan [8] was used. The ulcer was induced by administering aspirin 200 mg/kg. Forty-five wistar rats were divided into nine groups of five rats each. All the animals were fasted 36 hours prior to administration of aspirin. The experimental design is as follows;

- Group 1 - Distilled water
- Group 2 - *Musa sapientum* 250 mg/kg (MS 250)
- Group 3 - *Musa sapientum* 500 mg/kg (MS 500)
- Group 4 - *Musa sapientum* 1000 mg/kg (MS 1000)
- Group 5 - *Musa sapientum* 250 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 250) (1:1)
- Group 6 - *Musa sapientum* 500 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 500) (1:1)
- Group 7 - *Musa sapientum* 1000 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 1000) (1:1)
- Group 8 - Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (VITC)
- Group 9 - Omeprazole 20 mg/kg (OME)

Gastric ulcers were induced in the rats by administering aspirin 200 mg/kg orally in 10% Tween 80 solution 30 minutes prior to administration of the test drugs. Three (3) hours later, anaesthetic ether was used in sacrificing the animals and their stomachs opened along the greater curvature and ulceration were scored.

2.5.2 Ethanol induced ulcer model

A modified method of Rasika et al. [9] was used. The ulcer was induced by administering ethanol. Forty-five wistar rats were divided into nine groups of five rats each. All the animals were fasted 36 hours prior to administration of ethanol. The experimental design is as follows;

- Group 1 - Distilled water
- Group 2 - *Musa sapientum* 250 mg/kg (MS 250)
- Group 3 - *Musa sapientum* 500 mg/kg (MS 500)
- Group 4 - *Musa sapientum* 1000 mg/kg (MS 1000)
- Group 5 - *Musa sapientum* 250 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 250) (1:1)
- Group 6 - *Musa sapientum* 500 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 500) (1:1)
- Group 7 - *Musa sapientum* 1000 mg/kg + Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (MSVITC 1000) (1:1)
- Group 8 - Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (VITC)
- Group 9 - Omeprazole 20 mg/kg (OME)

Gastric ulcers were induced in the rats by administering 70% ethanol (0.5 ml/100 g) orally,

thirty minutes prior to administration of the test drugs. One (1) hour later, the animals were anaesthetized with ether and their stomachs opened along the greater curvature and ulcerations were scored.

2.5.3 Scoring of ulcer

Normal Stomach	-	0
Red Colouration	-	0.5
Spot Ulcer	-	1
Haemorrhagic Streak	-	1.5
Deep Ulcer	-	2
Perforation	-	3

Mean ulcer score for each animal are expressed as ulcer index.

Ulcer index (UI) was measured by using following formula [10]:

$$UI = UN + US + UP \times 10^{-1}$$

Where,

- UI= Ulcer Index;
- UN = Average number of ulcers per animal;
- US = Average number of severity score;
- UP = Percentage of animals with ulcers

Percentage inhibition of ulceration was calculated as below [10]:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of Ulceration} =$$

$$\frac{(\text{Ulcer index}_{\text{Control}} - \text{Ulcer index}_{\text{Test}}) \times 100}{\text{Ulcer index}_{\text{Control}}}$$

2.6 Statistical Analysis

All data obtained were expressed as Mean \pm SEM (standard error of mean). Statistical differences were evaluated using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnet's t-test. *P*-values <0.05 were considered significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Acute Oral Toxicity Study

Acute oral toxicity was done by using a modified Lorke's method. Acute toxicity study showed no obvious signs of toxicity in the treatment groups following the administration of fruit extract of *Musa sapientum*. The LD₅₀ of the extracts was greater than 5000 mg extract/kg body weight.

3.2 Anti-Ulcer Study

The effects of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* in combination with Vitamin C on aspirin induced ulcer is shown in Table 1. Deep ulcer and haemorrhagic streaks were observed in the control animals that received distilled water as treatment with an ulcer index value of 22.80 ± 3.40 . Treatment of the animals with aqueous extract of *Musa sapientum* (MS) at a dose of 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg resulted in non-significant ($P > 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index value (15.00 ± 3.98 and 14.00 ± 3.33), while 1000 mg/kg caused a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index (13.20 ± 1.50) as compared with the control animals. An insignificant ($P > 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index was observed in animals administered the mixture of MS 250 mg/kg and Vitamin C, and the mixture of MS 500 mg/kg and Vitamin C. MS 1000 mg/kg and Vitamin C 100 mg/kg mixture had a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index (10.00 ± 2.10) which was more than MS 1000 mg/kg dose. Vitamin C 100 mg/kg caused a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index when used alone. The standard drug of treatment (Omeprazole 20 mg/kg) gave an ulcer index of 4.40 ± 2.40 which was very significant ($P < 0.05$). The highest levels of ulcer inhibition was seen with MS 1000 (42.11%), MSVITC 1000 (56.14%), VITC (59.21%), and OME (80.70%).

The effects of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* in combination with Vitamin C on ethanol induced ulcer is shown in Table 2. Ethanol caused superficial, deep ulcers and perforations in the control animals. However, animals treated with aqueous extract of *Musa sapientum* (MS) at 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg doses showed significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the number of ulcer and ulcer index (11.40 ± 1.54 , 11.20 ± 0.98 , and 9.80 ± 2.89 respectively) when compared with the control group (20.30 ± 0.54). The ulcer index was further significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced when the *Musa sapientum* extracts were co-administered with Vitamin C 100 mg/kg (7.70 ± 1.14 , 7.50 ± 1.07 , and 6.50 ± 2.85 respectively). Administration of Vitamin C alone also resulted in significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in ulcer index (9.60 ± 2.23) compared with the control, but the decrease was less than that seen with the co-administration of Vitamin C with the *Musa sapientum* extract. Percentage ulcer inhibition increased with increasing doses of *Musa sapientum* and with co-administration of Vitamin C, with MS 250 mg/kg having the least inhibition (43.84%) and MSVITC 1000 mg/kg

showing the highest level of inhibition (67.98%). Omeprazole 20 mg/kg showed 88.18% ulcer inhibition and an ulcer index of 2.40 ± 0.40 .

Table 1. The effect of aqueous extract of *Musa sapientum* in combination with Vitamin C on aspirin-induced ulcer on wistar rats

Treatment	Ulcer index	% Ulcer inhibition
DH ₂ O	22.80 ± 3.40	-
MS 250	15.00 ± 3.98	34.21
MS 500	14.00 ± 3.33	38.60
MS 1000	$13.20 \pm 1.50^*$	42.11
MSVITC 250	14.30 ± 2.84	37.28
MSVITC 500	13.40 ± 2.89	41.23
MSVITC 1000	$10.00 \pm 2.10^*$	56.14
VITC	$9.30 \pm 1.46^*$	59.21
OME	$4.40 \pm 2.40^*$	80.70

All values are expressed as (Mean \pm S.E.M), n=5, * $p > 0.05$ when compared with the control using ANOVA followed by Dunnet post hoc

Table 2. The effect of aqueous extract of *Musa sapientum* in combination with Vitamin C on ethanol-induced ulcer on wistar rats

Treatment	Ulcer index	% Ulcer inhibition
DH ₂ O	20.30 ± 0.54	-
MS 250	$11.40 \pm 1.54^*$	43.84
MS 500	$11.20 \pm 0.98^*$	44.83
MS 1000	$9.80 \pm 2.89^*$	51.72
MSVITC 250	$7.70 \pm 1.14^*$	62.07
MSVITC 500	$7.50 \pm 1.07^*$	63.05
MSVITC 1000	$6.50 \pm 2.85^*$	67.98
VITC	$9.60 \pm 2.23^*$	52.71
OME	$2.40 \pm 0.40^*$	88.18

All values are expressed as (Mean \pm S.E.M), n=5, * $p > 0.05$ when compared with the control using ANOVA followed by Dunnet post hoc

4. DISCUSSION

An imbalance between aggressive factors and the maintenance of mucosal integrity via endogenous defence mechanisms is generally accepted as the etiology of peptic ulcer. *Musa sapientum* extract is one such herbal drug used in this present study to evaluate its anti-ulcerogenic activity when used alone and in combination with vitamin C in aspirin and ethanol induced ulcer models in rats.

The inhibition of biosynthesis of cytoprotective prostaglandins (PGE's and PGI₂) resulting in overproduction of leukotrienes and other

products of 5-lipoxygenase pathway is a principal mechanism by which aspirin induces ulceration [11]. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as aspirin are used in the therapy of rheumatoid arthritis, and gastric mucosal injury is an adverse effect with this use. Prostaglandin analogues (e.g. misoprostol) and proton pump inhibitors (e.g. omeprazole), amongst others, are currently been used to treat ulcers. These anti-ulcer drugs have also raised concerns following their toxicities such as diarrhea, uterine bleeding and contraction, hypergastrinemia, etc. which may predispose the patient to stoppage of therapy.

Ethanol has been reported to cause acute and chronic ulceration in the gastric mucosa through the release of superoxide anion and hydroperoxy free radicals during its metabolism [12].

Results of the present study show that aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* exhibits anti-ulcer activity on aspirin induced gastric ulcer when used at a very high dose of 1000 mg/kg and when co-administered with Vitamin C 100 mg/kg at same higher dose. On ethanol induced gastric ulcer, all tested doses of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* exhibit anti-ulcer effect, and this ulcer inhibition activity is potentiated (synergistic effect) by the co-administration of Vitamin C 100 mg/kg with *Musa sapientum* extracts. The antiulcer property of *Musa sapientum* has been reported to be as a result of its active component of flavonoid leucocyanidin (extracted via solvent fractionation) which protects the mucosa by stimulation of cellular proliferation, promotion of mucus secretion, as well as increasing mucus resistance [13]. Vitamin C potentiated the antiulcer activity of *Musa sapientum* due to the antioxidant effect of Vitamin C in decreasing oxidative damage to the gastric mucosa by scavenging free radicals and N-nitroso compounds (NOC), as well as in the attenuation of *H. pylori* induced inflammatory cascade [14,15].

5. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates a significant effect of aqueous extract of unripe fruit of *Musa sapientum* (Banana) and Vitamin C in reducing gastric ulceration in ulcer-induced animal models. The study shows a synergistic effect between *Musa sapientum* and Vitamin C in ulcer inhibition. Thus, this study concludes that Vitamin

C potentiates the anti-ulcerogenic effect of unripe fruits of *Musa sapientum* in wistar rats.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors hereby declare that "Principles of laboratory animal care" (NIH publication No. 85-23, revised 1985) were followed, as well as specific national laws where applicable. All experiments have been examined and approved by the Delta State University's ethics committee for the use of laboratory animals.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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